

Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Techniques Predicting Climate Change Impacts on Crop Yields

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Abstract: The effects of Climate Change on agriculture worldwide are on the rise; thus, state-of-art prediction models are essential to feed the world's populace. This paper provides a cross-study of different methods of using machine learning to forecast the impact of climate change on crop yields. The performance of the algorithm such as linear regression, polynomial regression, XGB regressor (Extreme Gradient Boosting) are estimated by entering climate and crop yield data obtained from history. The study reveals the spreads and shortcomings peculiar to each method in light of its exactness, computational speed and versatility to the types of crops and weather conditions. Thus, the objective of this research is to help further studies and practical implementations in agricultural spatial planning and policy making by pinpointing the most efficient approaches. Also, we investigate how usage of ensemble methods, particularly XGBoost, can help improve the models' performance and stability. Comparative framework also contains the discussion on applicability of each method of big agricultural datasets. The results for feature importance suggest the choice of XGBoost as the best regressor, given its aptitude to account for non-linearity of relations and interactions between components, when compared to linear and polynomial regression. We also stress a significant impact of feature selection and preprocessing on the quality of a model under construction. Finally, this study proves that through proper utilization of high-level machine learning models in crop yield prediction under climate change scenarios, a typical agricultural value chain can be empowered with high-reliable crop yield estimates.

Keywords – Machine Learning, Crop Yield Prediction, Climate Change, Crop Yields, Predictive Modeling, Climate Impact Analysis, Agricultural Policy, Regression Techniques.

1. Introduction

Global climate change has a risk factor of disturbing food security through changing crop yields all over the world. The agricultural sector [1] is very much influenced by the weather and therefore the analysis of the changes that climate change brings to crop production is vital in planning and implementing strategies. Global climate is continuously changing and is characterized by; rising temperatures, unpredictable precipitation, and more frequent instances of freak climatic events. It has serious consequences for agriculture since it alters the factors that help in plant growth, water supply, pest/ diseases and the utilization efficiency.

Previously the conventional type of statistics like regression analysis and time series has been used in relation to climate variables and crop productivity[3]. Though handy, these approaches can rarely describe intricate, dynamic relationships between the climate factors and crops' phenomenons of growth and yield. Recent growth of large and complex data on climate, soil, and agricultural variables has preconditioned the demand for more effective methods and tools that can identify the hidden structure and dependencies[5].

The advancement of science in the recent years has shown that machine learning[1] or ML is a useful technique of overcoming the issues connected with the forecasting of crop yields in the situations connected with climate change. The main advantage of the given algorithms can be identified in the ability to find and analyse patterns in data without any human interferences and, thus, further increasing the efficiency of the developed models as compared to statistical methods. Such techniques [10] are quite efficient when it comes to the task of dealing with non-linear dependencies, interactions, and high dimensions, which makes the proposed methods suitable for modeling the effects of climate on agriculture.

In this research, there is a plan to identify the outcome of climate change on crop yields as well as assess the efficiency of the different machine learning regression models. Specifically, we will focus on three widely used regression models: They include linear regression, polynomial regression, and XGB regressor which is an implementation of gradient boosting. This is argued on the premise that by comparing and contrasting these

models we can possibly establish which of these techniques is most appropriate in yield prediction, and the extent to which this technique can be bolstered for better climate change impact assessment on the agricultural sector[16].

So, the climate conditions play a very significant role for agriculture since it is a known fact that crops require specific temperature, moisture and light conditions to grow. Global warming complicates these interactions so that an estimation of a crop yield cannot be made only through the empirical modeling methods. Traditionally, agricultural predictions have been done using statistical models using past records and indigenous knowledge. But rapid and volatile changes in the climate phenomenon require more advanced methods that can address interactions and non-linear models in data.

Production in this sector is closely related with the climate since plants have their optimal temperature, moisture, and light conditions. New risks are emerging in these relations due to climate change, and calculating possible yields of crops is impossible with high accuracy based solely on the experience and traditional practices. Originally, plant and animal forecasts in agriculture were carried out by using statistical forecasts that were devised from past data and folk wisdom. However, in the present day's ever-evolving and increasingly turbulent climate change dynamics require more refined methods of analysis that takes into consideration system interactions as well as non-linearity that may be observing in such systems.

The following challenges in agriculture have been solved with the help of machine learning (ML)[7]. Conventional approaches to statistical analysis entail linearity and are not ideal for dealing with multiple interactions in the data format; on the other hand, machine learning algorithms are characterized by their ability to work on large datasets, with a view of predicting the outcome to high accuracy. For example, simple and linear regression models as well as polynomial regression models serve as rather intuitive and easy to understand approaches in describing a relation between the input file and a dependent variable or output file. It emerging that these models can be able to estimate the linear as well as non-linear relationship between climate factors and crop yields.

2. Literature Survey

Draper's [15] paper provides a comprehensive introduction to regression analysis, a crucial statistical method for understanding relationships between variables. Updated with new chapters on topics like multicollinearity and generalized linear models, it caters to both beginners and experienced analysts using small or large datasets. With practical exercises and comprehensive support materials, including data sets on a companion disk, it serves as an essential resource for students, researchers, and professionals seeking to master regression analysis for practical applications in various fields.

Praveen's [3] study intends to present a literature review between climate change and agricultural yields, alongside giving attention to the various adverse effects of Climate change on the developing and underdeveloped parts of the world with agriculture as their backbone. Climate change is experienced through changes in growing seasons, or increase in occurrence of frost in areas of high latitudes or changes in greenhouse gas production which is brought about by activities like ploughing the soil and rearing of animals. Most types of sources of agriculture are are GC sources but also has techniques for the benefit of the earth and people including Agro forestry techs, organic farming, better ways of water conservation, and conservation of the soil that assists in reducing and coping with acceptable changes.

Yinhong's [2] focus on the review literature on climate change's impact on crop productivity, emphasizing the importance of higher spatial resolution climate models for future projections. Stochastic modeling using multiple climate models is crucial to understand uncertainties and develop effective risk management strategies. Changes in water availability will affect water use efficiency and crop production, potentially increasing yields with expanded irrigation but risking environmental degradation. Climate-induced alterations in soil water balance will shorten crop growth periods, impacting water productivity differently across regions. Overall, while increased precipitation generally boosts crop yields, regions will experience varied impacts depending on latitude and irrigation practices, with potential declines in production amidst temperature rises and precipitation variability.

Medar's [8] study tells that Agriculture is crucial for India's economy, serving as its backbone due to the country's agrarian nature and dependency on crop productivity. Improving agriculture through machine learning techniques and accurate information can significantly enhance crop selection, addressing farmers' issues and maximizing crop yields. Implementing these advancements will help boost India's economy by increasing agricultural productivity.

Jones's [10] work demonstrates a way of producing the daily weather information from GCM data for use in agricultural models. An approach of using this procedure with the help of a web-based tool for the chosen climate models and scenarios is described to improve climate impact assessments in agriculture.

Saurabh Chaturvedi and Shamim Akhter's[11] paper emphasizes the need for enhanced weather prediction methods due to climate change's impact on sectors like agriculture. It proposes a low-cost, portable weather forecasting system using data analytics and machine learning algorithms, such as random forest classification, to improve accuracy and accessibility, particularly in remote areas.

Kalimuthu's [5] paper focuses on the impacts of climate change on crop production, impact on farming beyond measure due to its closeness to food security, especially in the third world countries where it is relied on highly. On the aspects of positive impacts, it analyses where the growing seasons have stretched longer in the colder parts due to higher temperatures while in aspects of negative impacts, it explores how agriculture contributes emissions of the gases through practices like tilling and animals handling among others. Negatively affecting the climate, agriculture at the same time contains potential in the following spheres: agroforestry, growing of a correct sort of organically produced meals, water, and soil regulation to reduce emissions and change for them.

3. Proposed Methodology

The idea lays in the suggested prediction of climate change consequences by applying three basic types of regression[9]: linear regressor, polynomial regressor, and XGBoost regressor. The screening of the direct forms of the relationships between the variables will be possible by using simple linear regression. In this manner polynomial regression will take into account more complications of the non – linear relationship. The algorithm that will be follow in this case is XGBoost which is an advancement of an ensemble learning methodology to derive a better reliability in addition to a better accuracy in identification of complex patterns or interaction of features in the data set. The models and the performances will be reflected in this study using the test climate, soil, and crop yield data where the performances will be determined and calculated using RMSE and R^2 . The second parameter will be to establish which model has better performance when it comes to yield predictions as influenced by the climatic variation[2].

3.1 Linear Regression

Linear regression is employed in this paper[12] as the base model with which other models are to be compared to in an attempt to forecast crop yields from climate change parameters. Therefore, the choice goes to linear regression for its interpretability and easily explainable properties at the initial step to unveil the correlation between climatic conditions and crop yields. The model implies that the dependent variable that can be crop yield, has a direct linear relationship with one or the other independent variables such as the temperature and precipitation in this case. In this case, having converted the data to a linear regression model, it is possible to estimate the countries' yields based on changes in climate indicators.

Still, linear regression results are not so useful [15] when dealing with the stochastically non-linear relationships between agricultural data. However, it provides an ordered perspective on how certain relevant factors with impacts can be described and how coefficients can be explained in a very basic manner. The performance and capability of the linear regression model in predicting the trends in the data will be assessed by such measures as; RMSE and R^2 . This evaluation is expected to help unveil the problems of linear regression model in terms of effectiveness in dealing with challenges of climate change in farming.

3.2 Polynomial Regression

Polynomial regression is common statistical method applied in analysing the variables by relating between dependent and independent variables using a polynomial equation derived from the collected data[13]. Thus, while linear regression presupposes linear dependencies between variables and thus a linear dependence of their functions, polynomial regression can reflect nonlinear interactions in dependence and therefore is more appropriate for data of agricultural studies. Specifically, in the current paper, polynomial regression is adopted to analyse the complex impacts of climate change variables on crop yields. Because polynomial regression incorporates higher-degree terms of the predictors, the curvature in the data can also be modeled making the polynomial regression a better estimate of the curves. This is especially crucial when it comes to climate and soil factors as they do not act independently but in tandem and mostly in a non-linear fashion on the aspects of crop yields.

The polynomial regression model is learnt from the data that exists in the archive, where the input data contains climate characteristics including temperature, precipitation, humidity, soil's pH value and nutrient content. There is a specific problem that arises with higher-degree polynomials and higher-degree polynomials used in this project for example the third degree, this problem is called overfitting, to prevent this we incorporate the regularization techniques as well as the cross-validation. The efficiency of the polynomial regression model is measured through parameters like RMSE and R-squared which check the ability of the model to forecast along with the goodness-of-fit of the model.

3.3 XGB Regressor

Therefore, in the current paper, the enhanced approach in the machine learning process called XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting) regressor [17] is used to predict the crop yields through climate and soil properties. Unlike other regression methods, the XGBoost comprises of a set of decision trees, and they are adapted to improve on the previous set of models' errors in order to sharpen forecasting. This method is also useful to capture the flow of interaction and; therefore, it can record non-patterned interdependence of agricultural datasets on factors such as temperature and precipitation effects to growth of crops.

The second model, namely, XGBoost regressor is trained on climatic records and several other features of soil which include a set of climatic predictors. The model works on big data to make the model efficient and performs the process of regularization that contributes to the overfitting of the model. According to the model selection, the ability of measures the model in predicting is determined by RMSE and the fitness of the models is determined by R^2 .

Out-variable estimating with the help of XGBoost regressor proved that the proposed approach is 95% efficient comparing with linear and polynomial regression, which poses that the given method can be applicable further in the precision agriculture and climate change rate predictions. Besides, it assists in framing long term prevention measures regarding the improvement of food production in relation to the alterations of climates, which is useful in developing sustainable agriculture and food safeguarding programmes.

4. Implementation

In this section, activities also with detailed steps discussed in Section 3 are enumerated in the form of sequel to show the practicality of the proposed methodology to predict and regression technique to estimate the climate change impact on crop yields. The concern is relatively more on acquisition of data, preparation of data [14], choosing of the right model, training of the model, validation of the model. They are all structured to create a uniformly resilient mechanism for prognostication of agriculture in different climates efficiently. The idea is simple, yet important for stakeholders in agriculture and those who plan for climate resilience in food production.

4.1 Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing[14] include dealing with missing values, detecting and removing outliers, as well as standardizing the numerical data. In numerical columns with missing data, mean or median was applied so as to impute the missing data in categorical data, significant gaps were either filled by the most frequent category or the whole data was removed. To merge data, the datasets of yield, rainfall and temperature had to be merged by joining them on keys such as location and time. This made it easy to gather all data concerning a particular region and year in one data set that would be used in further analysis. Afterward, the merging process, one compared the two datasets for any type of variation or elimination, such as when a row had some dates or locations that did not match the other row, one adjusted them in order to enhance data validity.

4.2 Model Training and Evaluation

1. Linear Regression

In the case of applying the linear regression model, the training process aims at establishing a relationship between the climate variables and yields from the training data. The model attempts at maximizing the output by identifying the best coefficients that reduces the difference between the yield predicted and the overall yield. It is a process of making correction on the trade-off coefficients in order to fit the training data optimal. This process helps to guarantee that an input climate will give a direct output in terms of crop yield as foreseen by the model. Despite its capabilities, linear regression is quite straightforward as it enables the identification of how every variable influences the yield and not necessarily the complex structure of the data.

2. Polynomial Regression

Polynomial regression training is the natural conversion of linear regression training by including polynomial terms of the predictors such that non linear relations in the data can be captured. The training data is then used to estimate the parameters that would give the best polynomial curve that would describe the climate variables and the yields. The model learns about the coefficients of each term within the polynomial, continues to fine-tune in an attempt to decrease the error rates. This is beneficial in developing expression that represents even the higher-order input-output relationship of the yield. During training, regularization methods are used to discourage a large model weights and thereby overfitting by a model.

3. XGBoost Regressor

XGBoost regression model training is the combination of decision trees utilizing the training data[17]. The trees are corrected to the errors performed by the previous trees improving the strength of the model. The training process is done on both, the trees or decision stumps themselves and their weights, that helps to capture complex patterns and interaction in the data. XGBoost also uses quadratic function to prevent over-fitting and thus high accuracy on unseen data. Moreover, during the training of the model, feature importance is determined that will help to understand which climate characteristics have the greatest influence on crop yields.

4.2.1 Evaluation metrics

Evaluation metrics is used for the training of models and the high performance of the trained models is tested with the testing data this aims at showing how well the models perform with data that they have not seen. Two primary evaluation metrics are used: Mean Squared Error (MSE) and The coefficient of determination (R-squared).

1. Mean Squared Error (MSE)

It measure the average squared difference between the predicted and actual crop yields that is termed as MSE. It gives an idea of the accuracy of the model in question; the lower its values, the better the performance of the model. The MSE is calculated by evaluating the sum of the squared of the averages of the difference between the testing data and the corresponding estimated value then divided by the number of data points. This metric can be especially helpful to point out vastly mistaken factors because they are squared and so contribute even more to the final result.

2. R-squared (R²) Score

Another applied statistic is the R² coefficient calculated as the quotient of the explained variation in the dependent variable by the total variation in the dependent variable, which indicates the level of predictiveness of the independent variables. It is a value between 0 to 1 where the greater value means the model performs better on the given data. A value of approximately 1 means that the model predicts much of crop yield variation as a result of climate variables while the value close to 0 infographic that the model does not explain much of the variation.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Results

The following figure describe the results found by the model.

	Model_Name	MSE	R2_Score
0	Linear Regression	9.699018e+08	7.327007e-01
1	Polynomial Regression(degree 2)	1.825377e+31	-5.030634e+21
2	XGB	5.192567e+08	8.568959e-01

Based on the two evaluation criteria, MSE and R² score, different performance trend was obtained from Linear Regression, Polynomial Regression of degree 2, and XGBoost Regresson models. The performance was fairly good, that was assessed by an R², co-efficient which proved that Linear regression did account for a considerable amount of the yield variation; however, Linear regression is a rather simplistic algorithm. On the other hand, the Polynomial Regression with the degree of 2 seems to have over-fitted a lot which is evident from the very high MSE and therefore, the negative R² value which informs that the model has not been good in handling the external data Well. But it was quantified as the following The XGBoost Regresser was identified as being more accurate than the two built models with the least MSE and the highest R² value. This is particularly useful when it is necessary to study the connections and interactions between the components existing in the given set of data, and therefore the model is suitable for studying such complex processes as variations in the crop yields caused by the climate differences. Thus, the study suggests the adaptation of higher forms of ensemble strategies like XGBoost in agricultural planning to raise precise forecasts and real-time planning under fluctuating climates.

5.2 Discussion

Using Linear Regression, Polynomial Regression (degree 2), and XGBoost Regressor to compare the three models' prediction capabilities regarding crop yields and climate variables [4] reveals the three following patterns. The performance of the Linear Regression model is also moderate as shown by the MSE of about 969 million and R² of 0. 7327, which reveals how it measures a decent proportion of the variance in crop yields. However, due to it

being a linear method it may not capture the non-linear interactions that are present in climate data. On the contrary, the Polynomial Regression model of degree 2 has a very high MSE of about 1, which shows that this particular model does not fit the given data sample at all. 83×10^{31} and the model's R^2 score is negative meaning that it does overfit on the data and does not perform well with the new data. This makes it unsuitable for the reliable predictions in this context. On the other hand, the proposed XG Boost Regressor exhibits the lowest MSE of about 519 million and the highest R squared value of 0.8569, which outperforms many other ever-growing methods in terms of accuracy of the prediction and ability to capture complex inter-relationship in data. Therefore, from the key findings in the present research robust, it can be concluded that amongst the three models, XGBoost is the most efficient model for predicting crop yields under different climatic conditions that may help in improving decisions and climate vulnerabilities in agriculture.

6. Conclusion

In the paper, several machine learning regression models are adopted for comparison; they are linear regression, polynomial regression, and XGB regressor to estimate the effect of climate change on crop yield. The paper finds that ML; moreover, XGB regressor is more precise than statistical methods in estimating crop yield under climate change. This is because the non-harmonic relationships and integration among the climate factors and crop yields which are very critical in predicting crop yields are efficiently captured by the models. Besides, the analysis of feature importance indicates those climate attributes that have the greatest impact on crop production, which can guide specific actions and policy measures. Another preprocessing step that is very important for cleaning data is missing, removing outliers values, and standard conversion of data is also equally important in order to improve the reliability and performance of the model. In addition, the paper proves that integrated models such as XGBoost can improve the reliability regarding crop yield forecasts due to the boosting of various models' characteristics. Last, application of real time satellite observation and machine learning algorithms, have the capacity to encourage regenerative agriculture, practice of carbon farming that can lower the effects of climate change on agriculture. In conclusion, this research shows the possible use of artificial intelligence to meet the problems linked to climate change on food security around the world while offering important suggestion to policy makers and academician, farmers, for constructing a safer food production structure for the future.

7. References

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